

THE STATE OF FORMATION OF STATE BUDGET REVENUES AND THEIR DISTRIBUTION BETWEEN BUDGETS OF DIFFERENT LEVELS

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Annotation. The effective formation and equitable distribution of state budget revenues play a crucial role in ensuring the stability and sustainability of public finances. This study examines the current state of budget revenue formation in Uzbekistan, focusing on the mechanisms of revenue distribution between various levels of the budget system—national, regional, and local. By analyzing existing legal frameworks, statistical data, and international practices, this research identifies key challenges and proposes recommendations for improving the fiscal system in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Revenues, local government, state budget, current expenses, inter-budgetary relations, local budget policies, real taxes.

The first processes of organizing budgetary relations consist in the formation of its part of income. Budget revenues play the role of a necessary financial resource for the implementation of the tasks assigned to it based on budgetary functions. That is why the main function of income is the formation of financial resources to increase the corresponding budget costs to practice. The revenue and cost components of local budgets are independent and at the same time interdependent categories. Each of them has its own characteristics. Revenues serve as a financial base for the activities of local authorities, while expenses serve to satisfy territorial needs.

In world practice, the following principled approaches to resolving the re-systematization of income and the provision of local budgets with taxable income are used between the branches of the budget system. The increase of private bases of taxation of territories does not always justify itself. That being said, we can say that the current status of the powers of local government bodies in the field of taxation is sufficient. However, the existing powers do not reflect in the face of a single complex that forms the implementation of active local budget policies, dividing them in relation to issues in the field of taxation. In addition, for economic development extirpations of the UZ of local government bodies the real necessary income does not seek to receive the right, but rather, they seek to receive surplus income at the level possible from the center according to the book of merit. This situation is due to insufficient improvement

of the system of inter-budgetary relations and the abstraction of legal situations at the national level is marked with.

In our opinion, it is necessary to redistribute existing tax income in the current conditions between the branches of the budget system on the basis of a permanent or extended period in a full or fixed share. Such an approach to a certain extent solidifies the tax base of local budgets, ensures a budget of different levels and various taxes in conditions of potential, an equalizing approach is maintained in the formation of tax bases of Regions. The current attached sources of income of local budgets are mainly taxes due to the fact that Real taxes are the most abundant in the tax debt of the existing taxes in the tax system. This situation is necessary for the current costs of most local budget nodes as a result of the lack of funds, temporary cash cuts are created, and the possibility of financing current expenses for the purpose of obtaining loans from the budget of the Republic is growing.

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